

Automated BIM-based Model Checking Workflows with Exchange Information Requirements

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Abstract

The success of building projects largely depends on the quality of project information. Therefore, project information management, including information requirements, establishes the foundation for effective project collaboration. Checking information requirements, identification, and resolution of information issues in complex BIM projects is a very time-consuming and costly process. Thus, automating the BIM-based Model Checking (BMC) process is indispensable for resource savings and efficiency. Through an applied research approach and qualitative methodology, the study investigated various BIM uses within the context of information requirements. Subsequently, the research introduced a five-stage BMC process, which involves adapting the traditional BMC process with an additional stage: Rule interpretation, Model preparation, Rules execution, Reporting check results, and Automated or Semi-automated code execution for resolving the information management issues.

To implement the BMC process, three distinct workflows are proposed. In Workflow A, the entire BMC process is conducted within a designated repository environment, enhancing efficiency by minimising the need for BIM model exchanges. Workflow B is conducted in standalone software or specialised BMC tools for BMC core stages of rule interpretation and

execution. Workflow C extensively employs openBIM throughout the entire BMC process, mainly rule interpretation using IDS. Throughout the case study, the predefined BMC workflows were implemented. The Level of Information Need framework was employed as input for the rule interpretation stage, defining information requirements for QTO and cost estimation. The study critically evaluated the opportunities and limitations of BMC workflows, discussing the potential and implications for project information management.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/pcJuDgB-1EU>

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